
**Quality assurance at the macro level: Comparing the current and
previous WoS snapshots**

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Motivation

The aim of the report is to identify any potential changes in data between or within database versions that may indicate quality issues. To do so it offers:

- a visual comparison
- between time-series over the last 10 years
- stemming from the current and previous KB database snapshots
- on several key indicators
- for national, sectoral and institutional entities.

The DZHW already conducts quality assurance testing at the micro-level for the KB's bibliometric databases before the tables enter the production environment. This testing is invaluable to ensuring tables and variables contain the expected content. This report supplements the current micro-level approach by examining changes in key variables between the latest two iterations of the databases at the macro-level of institutions, sectors, countries, and disciplines.

This report is not an exhaustive analysis of the databases' content, nor does it investigate any anomalies identified in the databases. However, this report probes the core variables fundamental to typical bibliometric analyses, serves as an overview of the current state of the databases, and highlights changes that may indicate issues with data quality that warrant further investigation to understand or rectify. Changes may arise through several means. For instance, the database provider may add or remove journals from indices, change the discipline classification, or change how the classification is applied. The KB may identify new or decommissioned institutions, which can affect publication output for particular disciplines, or countries may implement policies regarding publication practices that can exert a substantial influence on the content published over time. This report aims to provide users of the KB databases with an overview of any potential changes soon after the databases enter the production environment, so that these factors may be considered in analyses.

Set of indicators

The indicators included in the report reflect the core variables in the database that are fundamental to key bibliometric analyses and indicators. We provide context to the selection of variables and what information can be determined from their examination in each of the following sections.

We make two sets of comparisons in this report. For indicators where it is important to consider trends over time, such as whole publication counts, we compare the databases for the 10 years up to the year for which both have complete data. For example, the latest common year with complete data for the `wos_b_202404` and `wos_b_202504` databases is 2023, as data for the absolute latest year in each database are incomplete. Similarly, where citation-based indicators are used, we present the time-series up to the latest common year with complete citation data, which is 2021 for the `wos_b_202404` and `wos_b_202504` databases. This comparison highlights any differences in trends between the databases for the most recent decade.

For other indicators, it is most useful to compare changes between just the most recent years of complete data in each database. For instance, we compare the number of publications per discipline in 2023 from the `wos_b_202404` database against 2024 in the `wos_b_202504` database. Changes between the years are expected given we are comparing two different sets of publications. However, this comparison can also provide insight into structural changes between the database iterations, such as the addition or removal of journals from indices, which may influence indicators

at the macro-level. Such comparisons are also helpful in identifying new or removed institutions or discipline categories. Further, although users will likely use the latest database to produce a complete time-series for new analyses, it is important to understand how additional years of a time-series might differ to existing time-series presented in publications and reports.

Set of entities

We have chosen to compare the databases at the national, sectoral, and institutional levels. The countries chosen are based on those most commonly examined by the DZHW as countries against which it is useful and informative to compare Germany. We also examine the key German sectors: Universities (Uni), Fachhochschulen (FH), Max Planck Gesellschaft (MPG), Fraunhofer Gesellschaft (FHG), Helmholtz Gemeinschaft (HGF), Leibniz Gemeinschaft (WGL), the business sector (Econ), non-university hospitals (Clinic), and combined -Bund and Ressortforschung-Länder (Gov). The remaining smaller sectors, such as research associations, clubs, and international and foreign organisations are grouped into an “other” category. Individual German institutions are also examined via the KB’s institutional coding for Germany. However, as there are a large number of institutions, we present data only for institutions that have shown substantial changes in the indicator of interest.

Methodological details

We focus primarily on articles and reviews published in journals, as these are the most common documents used in bibliometric analyses. Unless otherwise stated, we examine content indexed in the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), and the Arts and Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI) WoS indices. As previously noted, we supply a shortened time-series for citation-based indicators to allow for a 3-year citation window. Wang (2013)¹ determined that at least 3 years is required for publications to reach their maximum number of citations per year, after which point the number of citations are likely representative of the publication’s long-term impact. As such, citation-based indicators include all citations received within the publication year and the subsequent two years.

Whole counting is used throughout the report. Although it is most common to use fractional counting, analysing variables using whole counts will still reveal potential changes in the variables.

Data for disciplines are presented based on the `sc_traditional` or Research Areas (RA) classification. The `sc_traditional` is a fine-grained classification that allows changes in specific disciplines to be analysed. However, as it contains over 250 categories, it is sometimes useful to use a higher level of aggregation to present an overview of the disciplines. As such, we also present some data on the RA classification. The RA consists of six broad groups: Life Sciences, Physical Sciences, Technology, Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities, and Multidisciplinary. These groups are mapped from the `sc_traditional` disciplines based on a concordance supplied by Clarivate Analytics.

This report is automated. Consequently, blank tables may appear in this report, but they are nonetheless informative about the indicator under examination.

¹Wang, J. (2013). Citation time window choice for research impact evaluation. *Scientometrics*, 94(3), 851-872. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-012-0775-9

Analysis

Publication counts: Total, selected countries, German sectors, and Research Areas

The count of items produced by selected entities is the most fundamental bibliometric indicator. Given publication counts form the basis of many indicators, understanding the time-series trend within and between databases can inform expectations about potential changes that may arise in other indicators. In Figure 1 we show the total number of documents of different types indexed in each database version. Notably, documents may be allocated to multiple types. We have allowed for double-counting between types, in that each document is counted toward each type it is assigned to. However, the total counts each document only once. Figures 2 to 4 show the whole counts of articles and reviews published by selected countries and German sectors over the last 10 years and in Figure 5 we show the distribution of publications by RA.

Changes in publication counts over time may reflect changes made by countries, the database provider, and/or administrative decisions. For example, it is expected that the `wos_b_202504` database contains a greater number of publications for the most recent years than the `wos_b_202404` database due to the continued indexing of items by Clarivate Analytics past the annual point in April at which the data is cut to create the KB databases.

Increases in publications over time also result from both the continued growth of the national science systems and WoS' ongoing indexation over time. Sharp increases for a particular country may represent an actual increase in the number of a country's articles published in WoS-indexed journals, such as due to policy decisions, or reflect the recent indexing of region-, country-, or discipline-specific journals. Decreases may reflect the de-indexation of journals in which an entity commonly publishes or the stagnation of a sector, such as due to funding or policy decisions or the de-commissioning of an institution. Substantial deviations between databases or decreases in the current database in recent years may warrant investigation.

A note on early access publications

Items of several types, e.g., Article, Review, Proceedings, were being indexed in WoS as "Early access" items for the year in which they first appeared online. In the subsequent year (and database version), their publication year and item type was updated by Clarivate from, e.g., "Article, Early Access" published e.g. 2023 to "Article" published 2024. This change appeared in Figures 1 to 5 as higher counts of items in the last common year (2023) in the previous database version than the current version. From version `wos_b_202404`, the KB WoS database now includes a variable to identify early access items. However, as only the only most recent year is used for this report, the same pattern of higher counts of items appears in 2023 in the following Figures due to the inclusion of early access items in `wos_b_202404`. Also, because each item is counted toward each document type it is classified to, early access items appear in both the "Early access" category in Figure 1, as well as the main document type, such as "Article".

Figure 1: Number of documents in each database over time by type.

Figure 2: Whole counts of articles and reviews by country and database over time, part 1.

Figure 3: Whole counts of articles and reviews by country and database over time, part 2. Please note the panels' different axes.

Figure 4: Whole counts of articles and reviews by German sector and database over time. Please note the panels' different axes.

Figure 5: Whole counts of articles and reviews by RA and database over time.

Journals: Total indexed and the number added or removed

The journals indexed constitute the foundation of the database. Year to year changes in the journals indexed reflect the database provider's curation procedures to introduce new content and remove content no longer meeting indexation criteria. The amount of and changes in content indexed can influence bibliometric indicators, particularly if changes are concentrated in specific disciplines. Figure 6 shows the total number of journals in each database over time, while Figure 7 shows the number of journals added and removed in each RA.

Changes in the journals indexed were identified by matching the titles of all journals indexed in 2023 in the `wos_b_202404` database to those with 2024 content in the `wos_b_202504` database. Titles were used as all journals have titles recorded, while some journals are missing ISSNs. Titles in `wos_b_202404` but not in `wos_b_202504` were considered removed, while titles in `wos_b_202504` but not in `wos_b_202404` were considered added. In total, 155 journals were added and 204 were removed. These data may include a small number of journals that changed titles. Some double-counting of journals between RAs may also occur when a journal maps to two or more RAs.

Figure 6: The number of journals indexed in each database over time.

Figure 7: The number of journals added or removed between 2023 in `wos_b_202404` and 2024 in `wos_b_202504` by RA.

Excellence Rates: Selected countries and German sectors

Excellence Rates (ER) identify the percentage of an entity’s publications that are in the 10% most highly cited publications from each discipline and could be considered of excellent quality on this basis. ERs are a common indicator used to assess an entity’s performance, with an ER exceeding the expected 10% threshold interpreted as better than expected performance. ERs for the most recent years from the two databases are presented for German sectors in Figure 8 and for countries in Figure 9. As with whole counts of publications, we would expect general agreement between the databases, particularly in the earlier years of the time-series, so substantial deviations may warrant further analysis.

Figure 8: ERs, based on whole counts, by German sector and database over time. The black line is the expected 10% threshold.

Figure 9: ERs, based on whole counts, by selected country and database over time. The black line is the expected 10% threshold.

Citations: Mean 3-year citations of articles and reviews by discipline

The number of citations a publication could be expected to receive is dependent to an extent on its discipline. As such, we examine here the mean 3-year citations of articles and reviews by discipline. Mean 3-year citations (MC3) are the mean citations publications in each discipline accrued in the first 3 years after publication. We examine here in Figure 10 the last common year in both databases (top panels) to assess the retroactive effects stemming from changes made in the latest database, and the latest complete year in both databases (bottom panels) to assess potential structural changes and updates to the time-series. A greater deviation of disciplines from the central line indicates a greater degree of change in the mean citations of a discipline's items between years. The outlying disciplines from the bottom panels of Figure 10 are shown in Tables 1 and 2, along with disciplines where the previous threshold was zero. We use a threshold of a current MC3 of at least 1 for articles and 3 for reviews to remove disciplines with spurious changes due to low levels of citations.

Figure 10: The MC3 for articles and reviews in each discipline between databases, where colour denotes the number of disciplines with this combination of citations.

Table 1: Articles: Disciplines with a current MC3 of at least 1, where the MC3 decreased by over 20% or increased by over 50% between 2021 in wos_b_202404 and 2022 in wos_b_202504, or the previous MC3 was 0.

Discipline	Previous MC3	Current MC3	No. crnt pubs.	Perc. diff.
Tropical Medicine	1.9	2.7	209	45.0
Operations Research & Management Science	4.7	6.3	2676	34.2
Social Sciences, Mathematical Methods	6.3	4.1	503	-35.1
Mathematical & Computational Biology	5.0	3.2	6694	-35.2
History & Philosophy Of Science	2.8	1.8	2346	-36.3

Table 2: Reviews: Disciplines with a current MC3 of at least 3, where the MC3 decreased by over 20% or increased by over 60% between 2021 in wos_b_202404 and 2022 in wos_b_202504, or the previous MC3 was 0.

Discipline	Previous MC3	Current MC3	No. crnt pubs.	Perc. diff.
Film, Radio, Television	0.0	0.5	2	Inf
History Of Social Sciences	0.0	0.5	2	Inf
Literary Theory & Criticism	0.0	0.1	8	Inf
Mining & Mineral Processing	6.0	47.4	8	689.6
Limnology	4.4	18.4	10	318.2
Operations Research & Management Science	12.1	35.9	37	197.5
Humanities, Multidisciplinary	3.1	6.8	79	121.5
Physics, Atomic, Molecular & Chemical	3.3	7.0	13	110.0
Computer Science, Software Engineering	11.7	23.7	101	102.2
Women's Studies	2.0	4.0	6	100.0
Mathematics, Applied	3.6	6.6	87	86.2
Mineralogy	10.7	18.7	3	74.2
Robotics	24.1	40.0	23	65.9
Psychology	18.8	30.9	58	65.1
Quantum Science & Technology	13.1	21.3	32	62.5
Environmental Studies	17.3	13.8	296	-20.1
Pediatrics	9.2	7.3	2038	-20.9
Mycology	15.9	12.5	72	-21.4
Materials Science, Ceramics	29.6	23.2	156	-21.6
Green & Sustainable Science & Technology	27.1	21.2	2126	-21.7
Archaeology	7.9	6.2	42	-21.7
Evolutionary Biology	12.1	9.5	51	-22.1
Crystallography	11.6	9.0	144	-22.8
Statistics & Probability	8.0	6.1	85	-23.4
Acoustics	17.1	13.0	221	-24.0
Engineering, Biomedical	25.5	18.9	807	-25.8
Regional & Urban Planning	9.8	6.9	14	-29.8

Neuroimaging	16.3	11.3	48	-30.7
Computer Science, Theory & Methods	72.6	49.0	49	-32.5
Ethnic Studies	7.6	5.1	13	-33.2
Mathematical & Computational Biology	12.0	7.8	168	-35.4
Psychology, Mathematical	24.3	15.0	42	-38.6
Ergonomics	20.8	12.5	38	-39.7
Industrial Relations & Labor	18.2	10.2	42	-43.8
Agricultural Economics & Policy	17.2	8.2	53	-52.6
Microscopy	10.1	4.7	14	-53.2
Ornithology	9.1	4.2	30	-53.7
Social Sciences, Mathematical Methods	29.0	3.3	6	-88.5

Uncited articles and reviews: Percent by selected countries and German sectors

While ERs represent the most highly cited publications and mean citations tell us about what’s average, the percentage of uncited publications can tell us about the entities at the tail end of the citation distribution. When examining uncited publications, we expect to see a decreasing trend in uncited publications over time. This occurs because citation counts are based on the items indexed in each database and so, as the database provider continues to index journals, the likelihood increases that any publication will have been cited by the indexed items. In particular, we would expect that the percentage of uncited publications in the last common year would be lower in the current database than the previous database, as data added in the latest iteration “complete” the incomplete last year of the previous database. An increase in uncited publications in the latest year may reflect processing issues that require investigation. We present in Figures 11 and 12 the percentage of articles and reviews per German sector and selected country that remained uncited 3 years after they were published. Please note, the increase in uncited publications for FHG since 2019 stems from the publication of a large number of ingredient safety assessments by one FHG institution in 2020 and 2021.

Figure 11: The percentage of uncited publications in each database over time by German sector.

Figure 12: The percentage of uncited publications in each database over time by selected countries.

Disciplines: Changes in discipline classification

This section shows in Table 3 any changes that have been made to WoS' sc_traditional classification. This could include splits, aggregations or removals of a discipline, or the inclusion of a new discipline to reflect new and emerging topics. We identify changes in the classification structure by comparing the number of articles and reviews attributed to each discipline in the latest years of each database and selecting those disciplines where the number was zero in one year but not in the other. Disciplines with no prior publications but some in the current year suggest the discipline may have been recently added, while the opposite suggests the discipline may have been removed or merged. Changes may also reflect changes in spelling or punctuation of the discipline name. Any changes should be checked with WoS' published classification structure.

Table 3: Changes in the sc_traditional discipline classification structure between the previous and current databases

Classification	Previous pubs	Current pubs
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Figure 13 shows the number of publications assigned to specific sc_traditional disciplines known to have changed in recent versions of the database.

Figure 13: Time-series of sc_traditional disciplines previously observed to have changed.

Disciplines: Changes in articles and reviews by discipline

This section identifies the disciplines that had a substantial change in the number of publications assigned to them between the latest years in each database. Changes in counts of publications per discipline may reflect changes in the journals indexed, the classification structure, and any potential processing issues. As such, any large changes shown here may be worth examining.

We show in Figure 14 the 40 disciplines with the highest percentage increases and decreases in publication counts between 2023 in *wos_b_202404* and 2024 in *wos_b_202504*. The number shown next to each bar is the numerical change in publication counts. We have used whole counting. Disciplines previously identified as being new or removed have not been included here.

Figure 14: The 40 disciplines with the highest percentage change in publication counts between 2023 in *wos_b_202404* and 2024 in *wos_b_202504*, with numerical difference in counts.

Disciplines: Percentage of publications not assigned to a discipline

Figure 15 shows the percentage of publications in each database that were not assigned to a discipline over the previous 11 years. Complete assignment of publications to disciplines is important as citation-based indicators typically use field-normalisation to account for differences in citation practices between disciplines. As such, items missing discipline information are excluded from such analyses and so large percentages of, or large changes in, unclassified items should be investigated.

Figure 15: The percentage of publications in each database that do not have a discipline classification.

Metadata: Changes in pubyear, doctype, pubtype and items removed

This section details the number of items for which changes were made to key metadata in the latest iteration of the database or the items were removed. We look at changes in the recorded publication year, document type and publication type as these three variables are typically the key inclusion criteria for bibliometric analyses. We also examine the number of items that were present in the wos_b_202404 database but not in the wos_b_202504 database (removed items), and items present in the wos_b_202504 database but not in the wos_b_202404 database (added items). A change in metadata for a large number of items may be problematic, particularly if the changes are not randomly distributed, such as adjustments having been made to items from a particular journal or set of publications, which may affect counts and indicators for specific entities. Some changes can be expected as the database provider updates or corrects items. However, changes to or removal of a large number of items may require investigation. Notably, the documents examined are not restricted to articles and reviews, but any document type.

We identified changes in the metadata of in-scope items by first matching items between the wos_b_202404 and wos_b_202504 databases using the item_id identifier and then calculating the number of items that were added, removed, or had different metadata. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: The number of items with changes in metadata between
wos_b_202404 and wos_b_202504.

Crrnt year	Prvs year	Diff. year	Diff. src type	Diff. doc type	Added	Removed
2016	2016	0	512	125	0	0
2016		0	0	0	182	0
2017	2017	0	297	149	0	0
2017		0	0	0	926	0
2018	2018	0	86	223	0	0
2018	2019	11	0	0	0	0
2018	2020	4	0	0	0	0
2018	2021	5	0	0	0	0
2018		0	0	0	1492	0
2019	2019	0	17	378	0	0
2019	2020	18	0	6	0	0
2019	2021	2	0	0	0	0
2019	2022	13	0	0	0	0
2019		0	0	0	11919	0
2020	2019	3	0	1	0	0
2020	2020	0	0	770	0	0
2020	2021	19	0	0	0	0
2020	2022	10	0	1	0	0
2020	2023	5	0	4	0	0
2020		0	0	0	27379	0
2021	2019	2	0	2	0	0
2021	2020	236	0	18	0	0
2021	2021	0	0	2799	0	0
2021	2022	96	0	21	0	0
2021	2023	27	0	14	0	0
2021		0	0	0	29356	0
2022	2019	6	0	6	0	0
2022	2020	47	0	39	0	0
2022	2021	627	0	596	0	0
2022	2022	0	1733	7733	0	0
2022	2023	211	0	83	0	0
2022		0	0	0	44732	0
2023	2020	44	0	1	0	0
2023	2021	197	0	176	0	0
2023	2022	1171	0	721	0	0
2023	2023	0	705	12664	0	0
2023		0	0	0	87942	0
2024	2019	72	0	72	0	0
2024	2020	650	0	640	0	0

2024	2021	1566	0	1565	0	0
2024	2022	11349	0	11337	0	0
2024	2023	87348	0	86475	0	0
2024		0	0	0	3067441	0
	2016	0	0	0	0	10
	2017	0	0	0	0	9
	2018	0	0	0	0	9
	2019	0	0	0	0	96
	2020	0	0	0	0	461
	2021	0	0	0	0	989
	2022	0	0	0	0	3725
	2023	0	0	0	0	15261

Metadata: Publications from each index

The WoS database is comprised of several indices. The KB contract with Clarivate Analytics specifies that we receive data from the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), and the Arts and Humanities Citation Index (AHCI). The other indices are the Book Citation Index (Science, BSCI), Conference Proceedings Citation Index (Science, ISTP), Conference Proceedings Citation Index (Social Sciences & Humanities, ISSHP), Current Chemical Reactions (CCR), Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI), and Index Chemicus (IC). The inclusion of items from other indices can be problematic as these items may fundamentally differ from those in the three core indices in, for instance, the countries of their authors or publishing journals, which can influence citation-based indicators. As such, we examine in Figure 16 the number of articles and reviews in each index in the `wos_b_202404` and `wos_b_202504` databases between 2014 and 2024.

Figure 16: The number of articles and reviews in each WoS index by database over time.

Metadata: Missing metadata variables

Figure 17 shows the annual percentage of publications in each database that are missing particular metadata, including page numbers, journal issue and volume information, DOIs, titles, references, abstracts, and keywords. We could reasonably expect improvements over time in missing metadata, such as for DOIs through increasing uptake of this identifier, however increasing missing metadata should be investigated. Empty graphs indicate there were no items missing this metadata.

Figure 17: The percentage of items with missing metadata over time by database.

Institution and country data: Number of articles and reviews with missing data

Bibliometric analyses often examine indicators at the level of institutions or countries. Further, fractional counting can be applied based on institutions, with articles apportioned according to authors' affiliations. It is imperative for accurate indicators that most, if not all, items have institution and country data, as missing information removes otherwise valid items from analyses.

The items table of the KB databases holds a record of all available items, while the associated data about authors' affiliations are held, in part, in the items_affiliations tables. We have operationalised missing institution information here as publications that appear in the items table but have no corresponding information in the items_affiliation tables. We present in the top panel of Figure 18 the number of items in each database between 2014 and 2024 with no institution information. Additionally, items can have institution information but no country code – from which country counts are derived – and these are shown in the bottom panel of Figure 18. Large disparities between the databases or substantial increases in missing information should be investigated.

Figure 18: The number of items with missing institution information (top) and the additional items that have institution information but no country code (bottom) over time by database.

Author-institution links: Percentage complete by Research Area and discipline

Similarly to ensuring that all or most items have institution and country information, it is important for allocating publications to entities that authors' affiliations with institutions have been assigned for the majority, or ideally all, items. As such, we examine here the percentage of items in each sc_traditional discipline with complete links between authors and institutions.

In Figure 19, we see in the left panel the percentage of complete links for 2023 data in both the previous and current databases, highlighting any retroactive changes that may have been made in the current database. In the right panel is again the percentage of complete links made in 2023 in the wos_b_202404, now compared with the 2024 in the wos_b_202504, indicating potential changes between the latest year in each database.

Figure 19: The percentage of complete author-institution links by disciplines.

Table 5 shows the outlying disciplines observable in the right panel of Figure 19 that changed by more than 7 percentage points in the percentage of complete author-institution links.

Table 5: Disciplines that changed by more than 7 percentage points in missing links between 2023 in wos_b_202404 and 2024 in wos_b_202504.

Discipline	Prvs %	Crrnt %	Prvs no.	Crrnt no.	Change
Dance	51.7	63.0	107	136	-11.27
Literary Theory & Criticism	84.7	71.2	515	454	13.54
Literature, African, Australian, Canadian	75.8	58.4	91	80	17.44
Literature, Slavic	91.9	71.2	485	376	20.65

To provide context to the percentage of complete links observed in the most recent years, in Figure 20 we present the percentage of complete links made between authors and affiliations in each Research Area over the last decade in both databases, plus 2024 in wos_b_202504. Substantial changes between years or differences between the databases may require investigation of the cause.

Figure 20: The annual percentage of complete author-institution links by Research Area and database.

German institutions: German publications missing from KB institution coding

In Figure 21 we show the annual percentage of German publications, i.e. those where the German indicator is TRUE, that were not assigned a KB institution code through the institution coding process. Increases over time may be due to the foundation of new institutions that have not yet been integrated into the coding process. However, publications without KB institutions are typically excluded from sector-level analyses, so it is important to understand the extent of missing institution information.

Figure 21: The percentage of German publications in each database that are missing a KB institution.

German institutions: Changes in whole counts of articles and reviews

This section compares changes in the number of articles and reviews published by German institutions between the latest years available in each database. These tables can assist in identifying institutions for which substantial numbers of publications have been added, removed or otherwise changed in the latest database. They can also aid in assessing the degree of change in publication numbers for larger institutions, which may require further examination if considered unusual or excessive.

Table 6 presents potentially new institutions – these had no publications in 2023 in the wos_b_202404 database but more than five publications in 2024 in the wos_b_202504 database. Conversely, Table 7 shows the institutions that had at least five publications in 2023 in the wos_b_202404 database but no publications recorded in 2024 in the wos_b_202504 database. We also highlight in Tables 8 and 9 the larger institutions (with at least 20 publications) that had a change in publication counts of more than 40% between 2023 and 2024 in the wos_b_202404 and wos_b_202504 databases.

Table 6: Institutions with more than 5 publications in 2024 in wos_b_202504 that had no publications in 2023 in wos_b_202404.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs
6329	Deutsches Zentrum für Psychische Gesundh	0	366
4089	Max-Planck-Institut für Physik und Astro	0	338

5542	Munich Center for Quantum Science and Te	0	217
6415	Heinz Maier-Leibnitz Zentrum	0	154
6347	Center for Mind, Brain and Behavior	0	147
6356	Cluster of Excellence on Plant Sciences	0	112
5682	Frankfurt Cancer Institute	0	111
6385	Center for Integrated Quantum Science an	0	98
6358	Center for Scalable Data Analytics and A	0	80
5611	Helmholtz-Institut für Metabolismus-, Ad	0	58
6297	Berlin School of Economics	0	57
6446	Center for Intervention and Research on	0	57
6438	LPI – Leibniz-Zentrum für Photonik in de	0	53
6444	Leibniz Gesundheitstechnologien: Ein For	0	53
6296	Lamarr - Institut für Maschinelles Lerne	0	47
6332	Niedersächsisches Zentrum für Biomedizin	0	35
6400	ScaDS.AI	0	35
6369	Helmholtz AI	0	34
760	Robert Bosch Stiftung GmbH	0	31
6445	OCM Klinik GmbH	0	31
6324	Forschungscampus STIMULATE	0	29
6375	Tübingen AI Center	0	25
5765	Technische Universität Nürnberg	0	24
6351	General Electric Deutschland Holding Gmb	0	21
6532	Naturschutzbund Deutschland (NABU) e.V.	0	21
6342	Rigaku Europe SE	0	18
6360	Google Deutschland	0	17
6449	CeGaT GmbH	0	17
6363	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft e.V.	0	16
6345	Bremen International Graduate School of	0	15
6435	Helmholtz Information & Data Science Aca	0	15
6563	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Chirurgie e.V.	0	15
6281	TSG ResearchLab gGmbH	0	14
6286	Continental AG	0	14
4560	Bundesdeutsche Arbeitsgemeinschaft für V	0	13
6331	MVZ Medizinische Genetik Mainz	0	13
6572	RIFCON GmbH	0	13
6336	BasCat - UniCat BASF JointLab	0	12
6409	EFCNI - European Foundation for the Care	0	12
6552	Materialprüfungsamt Nordrhein-Westfale	0	12
6311	Cytel Inc.	0	11
6293	Amazon Deutschland	0	10
6374	Microsoft Germany	0	10
6420	Nord-Ostdeutsche Gesellschaft für Gynäko	0	10
6432	Lumileds Germany GmbH	0	10

6553	Institut für Grenzgebiete der Psychologi	0	10
5473	Leibniz-Institut für Geschichte und Kult	0	9
5985	Deutsche Nationalbibliothek	0	9
6289	Wintershall Dea AG	0	9
6306	Johnson & Johnson GmbH	0	9
6321	attocube systems AG	0	9
6359	PharMetrX	0	9
6377	Brockmann Consult GmbH	0	9
6431	Kassenärztliche Vereinigung Bayerns (KVB	0	9
6501	Voith GmbH & Co. KGaA	0	9
6530	Ramboll Germany	0	9
6582	BSBI-Berlin School of Business and Innov	0	9
6302	Stiftung Deutsche Depressionshilfe und S	0	8
6340	BioMed X GmbH	0	8
6506	AIR LIQUIDE Deutschland GmbH	0	8
6511	Corteva Agriscience Germany GmbH	0	8
6528	HELLA GmbH & Co. KGaA	0	8
6534	sbp se - schlaich bergemann partner	0	8
6085	ISDC - International Security and Develo	0	7
6300	Klinikum Mutterhaus der Borromäerinnen g	0	7
6317	Muehlhan Holding GmbH	0	7
6348	NVIDIA Deutschland	0	7
6379	Vector Informatik GmbH	0	7
6535	International Solar Energy Research Cent	0	7
6538	Sysmex Deutschland GmbH	0	7
6158	VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH	0	6
6378	Institut für ImplantatTechnologie und Bi	0	6
6402	Steinbeis-Stiftung für Wirtschaftsförder	0	6
6429	Vandage GmbH	0	6
6436	European Paediatric Association, the Uni	0	6
6441	Deutsche Multiple Sklerose Gesellschaft,	0	6
6541	Institut für Luft- und Kältetechnik geme	0	6
6570	PETA Science Consortium International e.	0	6

Table 7: Institutions with no publications in 2024 in wos_b_202504 that had more than 5 publications in 2023 in wos_b_202404.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs
813	Europäisches Laboratorium für Molekularb	411	0
5160	Universitäts Herzzentrum Freiburg Bad Kr	197	0
5477	Leibniz-Institut für Photonische Technol	187	0
3540	DWI an der RWTH Aachen e.V.	124	0
548	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	79	0

798	Institut für medizinischen Arbeits- und	44	0
1126	Fraunhofer-Institutszentrum Schloss Birl	21	0
5591	Berufsverband der Augenärzte Deutschland	21	0
702	ISEG Institut für Sozialmedizin, Epidemi	17	0
1410	Institut für Sozialmedizin, Epidemiologi	17	0
500	Bezirkskrankenhaus Augsburg Klinik für P	13	0
4134	Herder-Institut für historische Ostmitte	9	0
6102	Retinologische Gesellschaft e. V.	9	0
193	Bayerische Zentrum für Angewandte Energi	8	0
6124	AVL Deutschland Netzwerk	7	0
1535	Deutsche Edelstahlwerke GmbH	6	0
2731	Lionex GmbH	6	0
4745	Hochschule für Musik Detmold	6	0
6103	Vector Consulting Services (VCS) GmbH	6	0
6175	TOMTEC Imaging Systems GmbH	6	0

Table 8: Institutions with more than 20 publications in 2023 in wos_b_202404 that increased in publication counts by over 40% in 2024 in wos_b_202504.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs	Perc. diff.
72	Deutsches Diabetes-Zentrum (DDZ)	42	158	276.2
6210	Sammelkategorie Vereine, Stiftungen	23	84	265.2
1082	Max-Planck-Institut für Chemie (Otto-Hah	228	776	240.4
6203	Munich Center for Machine Learning	39	98	151.3
6155	Bayerische Zentrum für Krebsforschung (B	79	174	120.3
6262	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather	25	53	112.0
1144	Fraunhofer-Institut für Physikalische Me	28	59	110.7
5913	Max Planck School of Cognition	21	43	104.8
643	Fachhochschule Dortmund	29	58	100.0
5721	Kerckhoff-Klinik GmbH	59	114	93.2
5975	European Virus Bioinformatics Center	27	49	81.5
1096	European Space Agency	32	57	78.1
624	Westfälische Hochschule Gelsenkirchen Bo	27	48	77.8
1632	AMO GmbH - Gesellschaft für Angewandte M	21	37	76.2
1214	UCB Pharma GmbH	25	44	76.0
895	Nordwestdeutsche Forstliche Versuchsanst	24	40	66.7
48	Leibniz-Institut für Atmosphärenphysik (41	68	65.9
23	Institut für Angewandte Geophysik	35	58	65.7
417	Berufsgenossenschaftliche Kliniken Bergm	30	49	63.3
49	Leibniz-Institut für Agrarentwicklung in	50	80	60.0
1053	Max-Planck-Institut für Herz- und Lungen	91	145	59.3
791	Sanitätsakademie der Bundeswehr, Ernst-v	63	100	58.7

821	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (DAI)	26	41	57.7
573	Technische Hochschule Nürnberg Georg Sim	40	63	57.5
4164	Leibniz-Institut für Deutsche Sprache (I	23	36	56.5
205	Naturkundemuseum Karlsruhe	36	56	55.6
610	Technische Hochschule Ostwestfalen-Lippe	173	268	54.9
1085	Max-Planck-Institut für Biophysik	80	123	53.8
355	Klinikum der Stadt Ludwigshafen gGmbH	46	70	52.2
5660	Heidelberger Institut für Radioonkologie	57	85	49.1
1152	Fraunhofer-Institut für Lasertechnik (IL	43	64	48.8
5879	HMU Health and Medical University Potsda	76	113	48.7
274	Robert-Bosch-Krankenhaus	143	211	47.6
486	Klinikum Chemnitz gGmbH	36	53	47.2
150	Europa-Universität Flensburg	45	66	46.7
5674	BMW GROUP	69	101	46.4
12	RWI - Leibniz-Institut für Wirtschaftsfo	35	51	45.7
841	Bundesamt für Naturschutz (BfN)	22	32	45.5
6215	Berlin Institute for the Foundations of	37	53	43.2
6018	Deutscher Verein des Gas- und Wasserfach	21	30	42.9
148	Europa-Universität Viadrina Frankfurt (O	54	77	42.6
1005	Restkategorie MPG, ohne eindeutige Insti	118	168	42.4
5771	Max-Planck-Institut für biologische Inte	31	44	41.9
609	Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Be	48	68	41.7
5508	EUROfusion Consortium Research Instituti	32	45	40.6
1076	Max-Planck-Institut für Entwicklungsbiol	104	146	40.4
5293	Biomedical Research in Endstage and Obst	82	115	40.2

Table 9: Institutions with more than 20 publications in 2023 in wos_b_202404 that decreased in publication counts by over 40% in 2024 in wos_b_202504.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs	Perc. diff.
1481	Fresenius SE & Co. KGaA	39	23	-41.0
452	St.-Antonius-Hospital Eschweiler	36	21	-41.7
5371	Heidelberg Institute for Stem Cell Techn	42	24	-42.9
915	Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtsch	58	33	-43.1
1568	Bruker Daltonik GmbH	37	21	-43.2
598	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	43	23	-46.5
5140	Restkategorie Universitätskliniken Münch	206	85	-58.7

Authors: Median number of authors by Research Area and discipline

The median number of authors on a paper can be informative about patterns of collaboration and their potential implications for fractional counting. For instance, increasing levels of inter-sector or international collaboration could result in decreased publication counts for individual sectors or countries when using fractional counting. As such, understanding changes in authorship patterns can provide some insight into potential macro-level changes for entities.

We show in the left panel of Figure 22 the median number of authors per sc_traditional discipline in 2023 in both databases, and in the right panel the median number of authors per discipline in 2023 in the wos_b_202404 database compared to 2024 in the wos_b_202504 database.

While little change is expected to be seen in the left-hand panel of Figure 22 as the number of authors on a paper is unlikely to change between databases, differences in the right-hand panel indicate potential changes in disciplines' collaboration patterns. Disciplines for which the median number of authors changed by more than 1, based on the right-hand panel of Figure 22, are shown in Table 10.

Figure 22: Median number of authors per discipline between databases, where colour denotes the number of disciplines with this combination of median authors.

Table 10: Disciplines where the median number of authors changed by more than 1 between 2023 in wos_b_202404 and 2024 in wos_b_202504.

Discipline	Previous median authors	Current median authors	Diff.
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Source items: Percentage by Research Area and discipline

Source items refer to whether the publications on the reference list of an indexed publication are also indexed in the database, as opposed to non-source items that are not indexed. Only source items are included in citation counts and so understanding the percentage of items cited that are also source can give an indication of the depth of WoS' coverage of a discipline. That is, if a large number of indexed items' sources are not indexed, the reverse is also likely true and a large number of citations of indexed items are also missing, which has the effect of reducing citation counts for disciplines with lower coverage, such as the arts and humanities.

The percentage of references that are source items is expected to increase over time as the database provider continues to index journals and makes efforts to improve coverage of journals from disciplines with known low coverage. The percentage is not likely to ever reach 100% however, as authors will continue to cite items outside of the scope or coverage of WoS.

We show in the left-hand panel of Figure 23 the percentage of references that are source items per sc_traditional discipline in 2023 in both databases, and in the right-hand panel the percentage of references that are source items per discipline in 2023 in the wos_b_202404 database compared to 2024 in the wos_b_202504 database.

It is in the right-hand panel that the effect of recently indexed journals may become apparent, where an increase in the percentage of source items may be seen if the journal is often cited within a discipline. The disciplines with a change in the percentage of indexed references of more than five percentage points between databases, based on the right-hand panel of Figure 23, are shown in Table 11. Longer term trends can be seen in Figure 24 where we present the percentage of reference that are source items per Research Area over the last ten common years of both databases.

Figure 23: The percentage of cited items that are source items per sc_traditional discipline by database, where colour denotes the number of disciplines with this combination of source references.

Figure 24: The percentage of references that are source items by Research Area and database over time.

Table 11: Disciplines where the percentage of indexed references changed by 3 or more percentage points between 2023 in wos_b_202404 and 2024 in wos_b_202504.

Discipline	Prvs % source	Crrnt % source	Change
Humanities, Multidisciplinary	31.4	38.1	6.7
Architecture	33.7	38.9	5.2
Dance	23.1	28.0	4.9
Poetry	9.6	13.6	4.0
Film, Radio, Television	19.8	23.7	3.8
Integrative & Complementary Medicine	77.6	81.0	3.4
Psychology, Psychoanalysis	36.7	33.3	-3.4